

Iodine catalyzed selective *O*-alkylation of alcohols with orthoesters^ψ

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Abstract : In the present communication *O*-alkylation of a number of allylic and benzylic alcohols has been described.

Keywords : Iodine, alcohols, orthoesters.

Iodine has been employed as catalyst for a variety of organic transformations such as *O*-glycosidation, *O*-acylation, *O*-alkylation to afford benzyl-alkyl ethers from alkoxides etc. including our earlier report on iodine catalyzed 1,2 addition of alcohols to dihydropyran¹. In continuation of our interest in exploring the new potentials of iodine as catalyst for novel C–O bond forming reactions, we herein report a rapid and convenient iodine catalyzed *O*-alkylation protocol for allylic and benzylic alcohols.

R = Allylic and benzylic

R' = CH₃, H

R'' = CH₃, C₂H₅

Scheme 1

Several allylic and benzylic alcohols were converted into corresponding ethers when reacted with different orthoesters in the presence of catalytic quantity of iodine. All the reactions were conducted at ambient temperature by stirring various alcohols (**1a-h**) with trimethyl orthoacetate (TMOA), triethyl orthoformate (TEOF) and triethyl orthoacetate (TEOA) (2 mol equivalent) in the presence of iodine as catalyst (5% w/w of alcohol). All the reactions were complete within 30–60 min. The products were isolated by treatment with saturated aqueous sodium thiosulfate followed by extraction with ether. Non-benzylic and allylic alcohols failed to react and this is in conformity with our earlier observation. Unlike the earlier protocol, secondary benzylic alcohols were also con-

verted into corresponding ethers in high yields. Moreover the optically active secondary alcohol (**j**, with absolute configuration *S*) was converted into corresponding ethyl ether with retention of configuration². The alcohol and ester derived from orthoesters were isolated as by-products during this transformation (MeOH and CH₃CO₂Me in the case of TMOA).

In conclusion, the iodine catalyzed *O*-alkylation protocol is a selective, rapid, high yielding and milder than our earlier strategy for this purpose.

Experimental

Proton magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectra were recorded on Varian GEMINI-200, AVANCE-300, Varian UNITY-400 NMR-spectrometer in deuterio-chloroform. In the ¹H NMR spectra tetramethylsilane (TMS) (δ 0 ppm) was used as an internal reference. Chemical shifts were reported in ppm downfield from TMS and were given on the δ-scale. The multiplicity, coupling constants (Hz), and number of protons are indicated in parentheses and were specified as a s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), m (multiplet for unresolved lines), etc. Mass measurements were carried out on MicroMass VG70-70H mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV using direct inlet system and were given in the mass units (*m/z*).

General procedure :

Mixture of alcohol (10 mmol), orthoester (10 mmol) and iodine (5% w/w of alcohol) was stirred at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC and after completion of reaction (35–60 min), reaction mixture was quenched with aqueous sodium thiosulphate solution and

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Table 1. Iodine catalyzed selective *O*-alkylation of alcohols with orthoesters

Entry	Alcohol	Orthoester	Time (min)	Product ^a	Yield ^b
1	$C_6H_5CH=CHCH_2OH$	TMOA	30	Methyl ether	93
		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether	89
		TEOF	39	Ethyl ether	90
		TPOF	30	Propyl ether	85
		TMOF	30	Methyl ether	91
2	Geraniol	TMOA	45	Methyl ether	83
		TEOA	45	Ethyl ether	80
		TMOF	40	Methyl ether	87
3	$C_6H_5CH_2OH$	TMOA	35	Methyl ether	90
		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether	88
		TMOF	30	Methyl ether	92
4	$4-C_6H_5CH_2OH$	TMOA	40	Methyl ether	84
		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether	80
		TMOF	32	Methyl ether	85
5	$4-CH_3OC_6H_4CH_2OH$	TMOA	40	Methyl ether	81
		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether	79
		TMOF	30	Methyl ether	82
6		TMOA	40	Methyl ether	83
		TEOA	40	Ethyl ether	80
		TMOF	35	Methyl ether	86
7	$4-NO_2C_6H_4CH_2OH$	TMOA	60	Methyl ether	73
		TEOA	55	Ethyl ether	70
		TMOF	45	Methyl ether	76
8	$4-ClC_6H_4CH_2OH$	TMOA	35	Methyl ether	80
		TEOA	40	Ethyl ether	85
		TMOF	30	Methyl ether	85
9	$C_6H_5CH(Me)OH$	TMOA	30	Methyl ether	82
		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether	80
		TMOF	30	Methyl ether	85
10 ^c		TEOA	35	Ethyl ether ^d	85

^aCharacterized by ¹H NMR, IR and mass spectra.

^bIsolated yields are reported after column chromatography.

^cOptically pure (absolute configuration *S*), optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -31.0$ [$c = 1.5$ CHCl₃].

^dOptically pure (absolute configuration *S*), optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -4.5$ [$c = 2.2$ CHCl₃].

extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 ml). The combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated *in vacuo* and the product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel.

Ethyl 3-phenyl-(*E*)-2-propenyl ether : ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 6.50 (1H, d, *J*

17.4 Hz, olefinic H), 6.22–6.30 (1H, m, olefinic H), 4.15 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, allylic CH₂), 3.50 (2H, q, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃); IR 1625, 1203, 1070 cm⁻¹; mass (*m/z*) 162 (M⁺).

Methyl 3-phenyl-(*E*)-2-propenyl ether : ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 6.60 (1H, d, *J*

Note

17.4 Hz, olefinic H), 6.20–6.40 (1H, m, olefinic H), 4.15 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz, allylic CH_2), 3.40 (3H, s, OCH_3); IR (film) 1641, 1200, 1065 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 148 (M^+).

3-Phenyl-(*E*)-2-propenyl propyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 6.60 (1H, d, J 17.4 Hz, olefinic H), 6.20–6.40 (1H, m, olefinic H), 4.15 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz, allylic CH_2), 3.44 (2H, t, J 7.6 Hz, $OCH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.60–1.80 (2H, m, $OCH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.0 (3H, t, J 7.6 Hz, $OCH_2CH_2CH_3$); IR 1635, 1203, 1070 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 176 (M^+).

3,7-Dimethyl-(2*E*)-2,6-octadienyl methyl ether : 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 5.25 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, olefinic H), 5.00 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, olefinic H), 3.80 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, allylic CH_2), 3.20 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.00 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 1.60 (9H, s, vinylic CH_3); IR 1675, 1660, 1205, 1105 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 168 (M^+).

3,7-Dimethyl-(2*E*)-2,6-octadienyl ethyl ether : 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 5.25 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, olefinic H), 5.00 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, olefinic H), 3.80 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, allylic CH_2), 3.42 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.00 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 1.60 (9H, s, vinylic CH_3), 1.22 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1675, 1660, 1205, 1115 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 182 (M^+).

Benzyl methyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, aromatic H), 4.55 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.30 (3H, s, OCH_3); IR 1225, 1077 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 122 (M^+).

Benzyl ethyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, aromatic H), 4.50 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.55 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 1.25 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1230, 1087 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 136 (M^+).

Methyl 4-methylbenzyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.10–7.25 (4H, m, aromatic H), 4.40 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.38 (3H, s, CH_2OCH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, benzylic CH_3); IR 1228, 1097 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 136 (M^+).

Ethyl 4-methylbenzyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.10–7.25 (4H, m, aromatic H), 4.44 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.52 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, benzylic CH_3), 1.25 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1205, 1094 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 150 (M^+).

1-Methoxy-4-methoxymethylbenzene : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.22 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, aromatic H), 6.84 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, aromatic H), 4.38 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.36 (3H, s, CH_2OCH_3); IR

1247, 1176, 1111, 1035 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 152 (M^+).

1-Ethoxymethyl-4-methoxybenzene : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.22 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, aromatic H), 6.84 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, aromatic H), 4.42 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.50 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 1.25 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1246, 1175, 1099, 1035 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 166 (M^+).

Benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethyl methyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 6.82 (1H, s, aromatic H), 6.72 (2H, s, aromatic H), 5.90 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 4.40 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.30 (3H, s, OCH_3); IR 1272, 1196, 1050 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 166 (M^+).

Benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethyl ethyl ether : 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 6.82 (1H, s, aromatic H), 6.72 (2H, s, aromatic H), 5.90 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 4.40 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.48 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 1.20 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1247, 1189, 1099 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 180 (M^+).

Methyl 4-nitrobenzyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.18 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, aromatic H), 7.52 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, aromatic H), 4.42 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.42 (3H, s, CH_2OCH_3); IR 1520, 1344, 1205, 1104, cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 167 (M^+).

Ethyl 4-nitrobenzyl ether : 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.18 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, aromatic H), 7.52 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, aromatic H), 4.48 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.58 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 1.25 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1521, 1345, 1230, 1105 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 181 (M^+).

4-Chlorobenzyl methyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.35 (4H, m, aromatic H), 4.48 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.45 (3H, s, OCH_3); IR 1226, 1088 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 157 (M^+).

4-Chlorobenzyl ethyl ether : 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.35 (4H, m, aromatic H), 4.48 (2H, s, benzylic CH_2), 3.52 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 1.22 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); IR 1224, 1092 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 171 (M^+).

Methyl 1-phenylethyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.30 (5H, m, aromatic H), 4.50 (1H, q, J 7.2 Hz, benzylic H), 3.45 (3H, s, OCH_3), 1.50 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3CH); IR 1220, 1096 cm^{-1} ; mass (m/z) 136 (M^+).

Ethyl 1-phenylethyl ether : 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.20–7.30 (5H, m, aromatic H), 4.50 (1H, q, J

7.2 Hz, benzylic *H*), 3.38 (2H, q, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.50 (3H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, benzylic CH₃CH), 1.22 (3H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃); IR 1225, 1086 cm⁻¹; mass (*m/z*) 150 (M⁺).

2-[1-Ethoxy-(1*S*)-ethyl]-6-methoxynaphthalene : ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40–7.56 (3H, m, aromatic H), 7.62–7.82 (3H, m, aromatic H), 4.50 (1H, q, *J* 8.2 Hz, benzylic *CH*), 3.68 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.38 (2H, q, *J* 8.0 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 1.50 (3H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, CHCH₃), 1.22 (3H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz, OCH₂CH₃); IR 1270, 1179, 1101, 1020 cm⁻¹; mass (*m/z*) 230 (M⁺); [α]_D²⁵ = -4.5 [*c* = 2.2 CHCl₃].

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